

EXPLORING THE EFFECTS OF INTEGRATING NEUROSCIENCE PRINCIPLES IN CLASS ON STUDENTS' PSYCHOLOGICAL ENGAGEMENT AND ITS RELEVANCE IN THE NEW NORMAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Educators all around the world are always looking for new ways to improve the teaching and learning process, particularly in terms of increasing student engagement in class. Students' engagement has become of particular importance because of its impact on students' academic performance, persistence, and career choice. Several studies argued that schools and their stakeholders have numerous opportunities to affect students' brains and enhance school outcomes. This study aimed to explore the effects of integrating neuroscience principles in class on students' psychological engagement. A quasi-experimental two-group pretest-posttest design with two intact classes was used in the study. Neuroscience principles in education were integrated in the first group while the second group served as the conventional group. A standardized instrument was to measure the levels of engagement of students. Pretest and posttest on students' psychological engagement were given before and after intervention. Descriptive statistics such as measure of central tendency, measures of variability and frequency were used to compare the two groups before and after intervention. To find out if there was a significant difference in students' engagement between the two groups after the intervention, a one-tailed independent samples t-test was conducted. Based on the gathered data, the first group with neuroscience integration posed a higher level of psychological engagement in class than the conventional group. Hence, integrating neuroscience principles in class is capable of enhancing students' engagement. Further, the relevance of integrating neuroscience principles in the new normal education were deliberated in the study.

Keywords: neuroscience integration in class, student engagement